

**SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES OF EMIRI OF BUKHARA
SHAHMUROD MA'SUM**

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article is dedicated to the scientific gatherings held in the presence of Amir Shahmuradbi, the Sufi king who ruled the Bukhara Emirate.

Issues related to Islamic religion and, Sufism were discussed at the scientific meetings organized in the palaces of the emirs, mosques and, madrasas.

Keywords: Shaykh, hirqa, dervish sect, khanaqah, people of knowledge

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная научная статья посвящена научным собраниям, проходившим в присутствии Амира Шахмурадби, суфийского царя, правившего Бухарским эмиратом.

Вопросы, связанные с исламской религией и суфизмом, обсуждались на научных собраниях, организованных во дворцах эмиров, мечетях и медресе.

Ключевые слова: Шейх, хирка, секта дервишей, ханака, люди знания

In historical sources, the ruler of the Bukhara Khanate, Amir Shahmurad, is mentioned as a Sufi king and, "Amiri ma'sum [1, B.40]". Some of Shahmuradbi's philosophical and, religious views were expressed in the book "Ain ul-hikmat" ("The Source of Knowledge") written by him [2, B.61]. According to information, Amir Shahmurad created special manuals on jurisprudence and, legislation[<https://tegra.ph/BEGUNOH-AMIRNING-IBRATI-12-16>].

According to Abu Tahirkhoja's work "Samaria", "*When Shahmurad was young,*

he studied at the Mir Arab Madrasa for several years. He studied Sufism among other subjects, and, the Sufi way of life became the essence of his life [3, B.13-15]". Consequently, "Amir Shahmurad, who was pious from childhood, grew up as a beggar, studied at a madrasa, and, became one of the dervish leeches, had the qualities of a ruler and, Sufi [4, B.48-49]". Shahmuradbi's forehead showed signs of generosity, but at that time (in his youth) he entered the path of the Faqru Fano sect and, was a porter on the streets of Bukhara on the orders of his elder [13, B.31]. Herman Vambery writes, "He showed a tendency to religious (scientific) gatherings in his youth. He even changed his appearance and, put on a dervish dress, sometimes spending the whole day in houses and, mosques, engaged in zikr and, samo', and, at such times no one dared to disturb his pleasure.

In his free time, he used to hang out in the courtyard of Masjidi Kalon, and, for another year he was engaged in prayer, and, wrote his best work: "Ainul Hikmat" - "Fountain of Wisdom" here [5, B.158- 159]". Of course, Amir Shahmurad spent his salary allocated by the state on constructions, scholars and, students, he lived a life no different from dervishes. One of the historians wrote about Amir Shahmurad: "Qubbat ul-Islam" and, dar ul-khilafa was one of the last avliyullah sultans of Bukhara Sharif, whose blessed name is Muhammad Shahmurad Vali [7, B.150]. In the sources, he was called with such proud names as Amiri Kabir, Amiri Ma'sum, Amiri Ghazi, Amiri Jannatmakon, Amiri Vali and, Umar the Second [5, B.48]. According to the historian Khahramon Rajabov, "As a noble ruler, Amir Shahmurad thoroughly mastered Islamic sciences. Unfortunately, until now, this aspect of Amir Shahmurad's activity, in general, his personality, has not been objectively evaluated in the history of Uzbekistan. Our historians have a difficult and, at the same time honorable task of filling this void. In particular, Amir Shahmurad, as a connoisseur of works created on the Holy Qur'an, knowledge of the word (based on the views of Imam Moturidi), the

Hanafia sect and, Sufism, participated in various gatherings of scholars held in the palace in Ark and, outside Bukhara, and, resolved controversial issues. It is said that he preached various sermons in front of the people during Friday prayers. Amir Shahmurad wrote the work "Ain al-hikmat" ("Foundations of Wisdom"), imbued with the ideas of Sufism. In addition, he compiled a collection of "Fatavoyi ahli Bukhara" ("Fatwas for the people of Bukhara") related to the Hanafia sect. [8, B.36]". From this point of view, these works of Amir Shahmurad should be considered today as a rare and, valuable source of law in the study of the history of national statehood and, its scientific analysis.

Amir Shahmurad visited different regions of the emirate not only in Bukhara city, but also held trainings in the mosques and, madrasas on Sharia law norms and, issues related to their implementation. After serving as imam in mosques, he called the "supreme assembly" (Majlisi ali) and, gathered scholars, judges, and, scholars of hadith for it. In these meetings, based on the norms of Islamic law and, legal customs, he gave answers to the people's questions about fiqh problems [9, B.19]. Permanent scientific (religious) meetings were held in his presence.

For example, Amir was one of the mature and, potential scientists of his time. According to Ahmad Donish, *"In the Islamic era, there was no mujaddid like Amir Ma'sum Shahmurad. After all, it is worth calling him "Second Omar". Therefore, they see the virtues and, qualities that were not in Umar ibn Abdulaziz in Amir Ma'sum Shahmurad. He possessed the perfection of the justice of Faruq (Umar ibn Khattab) and, the poverty of Sulayman alayhissalam.*

Amir Ma'sum went to a madrasa and, studied. Entering among ordinary citizens, one of the sheikhs became a disciple. Due to his natural abilities, he acquired religious knowledge in a short time and, enjoyed the leeches of the Sufis (Mujaddidiya - Naqshband,iyya). [10, B.17-20]". His first murshi was akhund Muhammad Safar Khorezmi [8, B.36-38]. Shahmuradbi studied Sufi teachings, Islamic legal norms and, knowledge of obligations from Sheikh Safar, and, the

knowledge of the Holy Qur'an from three mentors, namely Hafiz Ashur, Nadir Baqi and, Niyazquli qari [9, B.18] .

According to the information, after completing his studies, Amir taught at Bukhara madrasa "Hidaya", Bayzavi's treatise "Kitab usul ad-din" and, Shatibi's works and, commentaries written on them. Shahmuradbi's son Miri writes that the emir knew "Shotibiya" and, its commentaries by heart. He was also a scholar of recitation, hadith and, jurisprudence, and, spent his life teaching students and, raised many students. Amir Shahmurad introduced the payment of allowances (stipends) to madrasa students from tax revenues. Amir Shahmurad (as we mentioned above) edited a book on Islamic Sharia called "Fatavoyi ahli Bukhara" ("Fatovoyi Amiriy") [11, B.5804]. But he did not have time to turn this collection of fatwas into a complete book. After his father's death, his son Amir Haydar finished this book [12, B.14]".

Literary evenings with the participation of poets were held under Amir Shahmurad. The famous poet Mujrim Obid gained fame mainly during the time of Amir Shahmurad. He worked as a messenger in the palace. There are opinions that Mujrim-Abid came to the attention of the khan because of his ode to him. Khan and, his children are praised in these odes. In fact, Mujrim-Obid was attracted to the palace by Mirza Sadiq Munshiy Jondari, a great wordsmith court poet who worked as the chief munshi of the emirate's cabinet during this period. He wrote many odes while working under the ruler. it is also possible that further studies will clarify this [7, B.375]. Consequently, Shahmuradbi organized meetings with many poets such as Mujrim Obid and, Mirza Sadiq Munshiy Jondari. The sources provide information about the emir's writing of poetry. According to Muhammadhakim Khan Tora in "Muntakhab al-Tawarikh", *"Shahmuradbi came to Jizzakh after midnight. Torches were burning in front of him. One of the people who were being looted and, captured (in Khojand,) read this verse aloud. Byte:*

***Dudi mash'al pesh – pesh, ohi mazlumon zi pas,
Gar ba in nahj ast mulkdorihon havas.***

(Content: The burning torch is ahead, followed by the sigh of the oppressed, and, in this way, the desire to take the land,.)

When Shahmuradbi heard this, he said, "Yes, he spoke correctly" and, read this verse:

So'fi shudani o'zbek ishkamai roh memonad.

(Content: Being an Uzbek Sufi is like a bump in the road.)

Shahmuradbi moved his people from Khojand, to Samarkand, and, ordered them to improve Samarkand,. [13, B.48]". This evidence also confirms that the emir is a poet.

In short, the scientific (religious) meetings held in the presence of Amir Shahmurad served the development of religion and, mysticism.

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